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An Overview of the current concepts in temporomandibular joint disorders

Sanaa R. A. Rao'of

Department of prosthodontics, Bab Al-Mu'adam Specialized Dental Center for Prosthodontics and Orthodontics

Abstract

Background: Controversy continues in the area of etiology, diagnosis, and management of temporomandibular disorders. This article, which is based on an assessment of both the past and the most recent basic science and clinical literature, reviews and summarizes the recent temporomandibular disorders literature.

Methods: To find the relevant studies addressing the temporomandibular joint disorders, a MEDLINE search was conducted, which was complemented by a hand search in selected journals.

Results and conclusions:- Because little is known about the natural course of the various classifications of temporomandibular disorders, and because most treatment approaches are reported to be equally effective (this may include but not be limited to the following: physical therapy, pharmacotherapy, behavioral modification management, psychological therapy, splint therapy, surgical therapy, orthodontic therapy and prosthodontic therapy), a conservative noninvasive management program is endorsed. Studies concluded that a majority of temporomandibular disorder

patients achieve good relief of symptoms with noninvasive reversible therapy.

Key words:- Temporomandibular joint disorders, myofascial pain dysfunction syndrome, musculoskeletal fascial pain, occlusion and occlusal splints.

Introduction:

In the last decade an interest in occlusion and the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) has expanded in many directions and from many sources. Although there is obviously a higher level of awareness about the importance of occlusion than before, there is also a high level of confusion about diagnosis and treatment of temporomandibular disorders (TMD), especially regarding the relationship between occlusion and the TMJ.

TMJ therapies that violate basic principles of occlusion are still in use. And we commonly see occlusal treatment, including orthodontics, prosthodontics, and maxillofacial surgery performed independently of any regard for the physiologic function of the jaw joints. Attempts to isolated TMJ problems as unrelated to the teeth have missed the fundamental fact that the condyles and the lower teeth have a fixed relationship to each other. Therefore, a more complete understanding of the masticatory system

E mail address of author
dr_sanaa77@yahoo.com

is important. Dentists today are expected to be physician of the masticatory system. It is a role for which no other medical specialist has adequate training. Equilibrium in the system cannot be achieved separated from the dentition, nor can stability of the dental arches be achieved in disharmonious relationship with the joints, the muscles, or the skeletal base [1].

The purpose of this literature is to review the current understanding of the TMD, etiology, recent classification and management with emphasis on splint therapy and occlusal therapy and how the prosthodontist can deal or manage those patients.

Methods:

To find the relevant articles, a MEDLINE literature search was conducted for the period from 1980 to June 2007. The key word “temporomandibular joint” was combined with the following key words (and combination thereof): pain, mandible, occlusion, temporomandibular joint disorders, temporomandibular joint dysfunction syndrome and orofacial pain. The computer- based literature search was further supplemented with a hand search of articles and book chapters. Whenever possible, reference was given to those articles that represented original research rather than to those that described a clinical case or opinion.

Temporomandibular Disorders:

A TMD is a collective term embracing a number of clinical problems that involve the masticatory musculature, the TMJ, or both [2]. The most frequently sign at presentation is pain, usually localized in the muscles of mastication, the preauricular area, and / or the TMJ. In addition to pain, which is

usually aggravated by chewing and other jaw functions, patients with TMD often have limited or asymptomatic mandibular movements and joint sounds that are commonly described as clicking, popping , grating , or crepitus [3].

Epidemiologic studies report that approximately 75% of the population have at least one sign of dysfunction (joint noise, deviation on opening, episodic locking) and approximately 33% have at least one TMD symptom (face pain , jaw pain) [4-6]. Signs and symptoms of TMD generally increase in frequency and severity from the second through the fourth decade of life. (fig.1) [7, 8]. The clinical tabulations report a ratio of approximately 4:1 of females to males seeking care for TMD. (fig.2) [9.10].

These prevalence figures may overstate the clinical significance of this problem, because many studies include individuals with mild transient signs and symptoms that many not require treatment. Indeed, of the large percentage of the population who have signs and / or symptoms, it is estimated that only approximately 5% to 6% are in need of treatment [5, 11, 12].

Fig.1.. Prevalence of age groups in sample of 1505 patients seeking TMD treatment at University of California, San Francisco, Center for TMD and Orofacial Pain between 1993 and 1995

Fig.2. Prevalence of females to males seeking TMD treatment is approximately 4:1 at University of California, San Francisco, Center for TMD and Orofacial Pain between 1993 and 1995.

Historically, a majority of the dental profession viewed occlusal disturbances as the most important etiologic factor. Later, others emphasized the significance of psychologic factors, and the battle lines between psyche and soma were drawn. Some people tried to minimize the conflict by suggesting that both occlusal and psychologic factors contribute to the development of TMD. When it became obvious that TMD encompasses a spectrum of various disorders, etiologic concepts based on a single factor lost credibility. This idea of a multifactorial etiology became more generally accepted around the end of 1970s [13]. This Controversy exists because of the limited knowledge regarding the etiologic and natural history or course of TMD. Some contributing etiologic factors are only risk factors, others are causal in nature, and others result from, or are purely coincidental to, the problem. A further development has been to talk about contributing as well as etiologic factors and to classify these as either predisposing, initiating and perpetuating [13,14].

Predisposing factors can be systemic (general health), psychologic (personality, behavior), or structural (occlusion, joint). Many systemic disorders may affect the components of the masticatory system, for example, influencing local TMD or causing changes of the joint structures. In general, a physician should manage the systemic conditions, but the dentist may take responsibility for local TMD treatment. The most common systemic conditions are rheumatologic diseases. Several epidemiologic studies have shown that individuals with impaired general health tend to suffer more frequent and severe TMD signs and symptoms than healthy people [13]. The role of psychologic disturbances in the etiology of TMD also is controversial. It is widely recognized that psychological factors may be involved in the pain perception process [15, 16]. Although the etiology of TMD has not been established, psychological factors have been implicated in the predisposition, initiation, and perpetuation of TMD [17-22] and psychological therapies have been found to be beneficial for some TMD patients [23-26]. Psychological factors have been implicated in several aspects of masticatory pain and dysfunction problems. First, stress-related muscle hyperactivity and oral habits have been suggested as etiologic factors. Second, psychological factors have been suggested to explain why some patients seem to be more bothered by symptoms and why only a small percentage of patients actually seek treatment. Finally, psychological conditions, such as depression, have been used to explain why some patients do not respond to conventional therapy. Results of studies evaluating personality

and emotional characteristics using a variety of psychological inventories and clinical interviews indicate that TMD patients have a wide range of personality characteristics and conditions, which may result in increased emotional problems and difficulty in coping with life events [21]. Laskin [27] has distinguished myofascial pain which is of muscular origin and more diffuse in nature, from TMJ pathology (disk displacement and other joint conditions). Pain, if present in the latter condition, is usually more localized. This division is widely used when psychological profiles are evaluated between different subgroups of TMD patients [19, 20, 28-31].

The question of what role occlusal factors play in the etiology of TMD has been answered with conflicting statements over the years. Occlusion is an important variable in the overall treatment scheme for clinical restorative and prosthodontic success [32]. Occlusion is defined as "the static relationship between the incising or masticating surfaces of the maxillary or mandibular teeth or tooth analogues" [33]. This relationship should be as balanced and stress – free as possible [32]. The concept of mandibular overclosure proposed by Dr. James Costen, an otolaryngologist, in 1934 was related to various ear symptoms [34]. This was expanded in the 1970's into mechanical displacement theory. This theory claimed that deflective occlusal contacts and lack of molar support were directly responsible for the eccentric positions of condyles in fossa and that these eccentric positions caused pain and dysfunction. This theory was based on the hypothesis that the condyles had to be in a central position for proper

function. This hypothesis has been disapproved by several investigators, demonstrating eccentric condylar position in many asymptomatic patients [35]. A recent study revealed that a positive association between missing mandibular posterior teeth and the presence of disk displacement was found. The authors do not suggest that replacement of these teeth will prevent the development of TMD, but their absence may accelerate the development of degenerative joint disease [36]. The second theory that evolved in 1970's was based on assumption that occlusal interferences or loss of molar support caused hyperactivity in the masticatory muscles [37]. The altered periodontal receptor input will adversely affect the sensory feedback mechanism and result in disturbed patterns of muscle contractions [32]. The patients tried to remove the interferences by parafunctional muscular activity or to stabilize the jaw in cases where occlusal stability was not present. Interferences were thought to be the direct cause of parafunction leading to jaw muscular pain and joint overload and dysfunction [1, 38]. Even if the influence of occlusal factors in the etiology of TMD at present is questionable and likely to be of minor importance, it cannot be ruled out as a possible factor. It may certainly be a contributing factor in individual patients. Occlusion is of great importance in all aspects of clinical dentistry, and the risk of introducing unfavorable occlusal relationship in restorative dental procedures must be minimized [13].

Initiating (or participating) factors that lead to the onset of symptoms are primarily related to trauma, parafunction or repetitive adverse loading of the masticatory

system. Overt trauma producing injury to the head, neck, or jaw can result from an impact injury, possibly a flexion- in extension injury, an injury while eating, yawning, or even from prolonged mouth opening during long dental appointments. A second form of trauma is associated with the sustained and repetitions adverse loading of the masticatory system as a result of parafunction. However, a demonstrated direct cause and effect relationship is still lacking between Parafunction and TMD [13, 39].

Perpetuating (or sustaining) factors, such as parafunction, hormonal factors, or psychological factors, may be associated with any predisposing or initiating factor and can sustain the patient's disorder, complicating management of it [40].

Diagnostic Classification of Temporomandibular Disorders:

Developing a validated diagnostic classification for TMD has been difficult because of the lack of clear etiologic factors, lack of homogeneity of the patient population, and the lack of knowledge regarding the natural progression of TMD. The American academy of orofacial pain's (AAOP) classification of the TMD includes a disparate group of TMJ (articular) and masticatory muscle (non articular) disorders. The following subclassifications are paraphrased from the 1993 and 1996 AAOP guidelines on TMD and orofacial pain.

TMD can be subdivided into articular disorders related to congenital or development disorders, disk derangement disorders, dislocation, inflammatory disorders, osteoarthritic disorders(non inflammatory), ankylosis, and condylar fracture (Table.1). These

subclassifications are very similar to disorders in other synovial joints in the body [41, 42].

Most congenital or development joint disorders are rarely accompanied by orofacial pain. They include agenesis, hypoplasia, hyperplasia, and neoplasia. Important exceptions that are painful are malignant diseases of the condyle, such as osteosarcoma, chondrosarcoma, or adenocarcinoma [43, 44].

The subclassification of disk displacement represents a disk-condyle misalignment and is subdivided into disk displacement with reduction or disk displacement without reduction [45-47]. Disk displacement with reduction is characterized by the "temporarily" displacement or misaligned disk abruptly improving its structural relationship with the condyle during mandibular translation resulting in an opening joint sound, for example clicking or popping. A reciprocal closing noise is of less magnitude and is thought to be produced by the displacement once again of the disk in usually an anterior or anteromedial position. The condition is very common and may represent a physiologic accommodation without clinical significance [48, 49].

Disk displacement without reduction, also called closed-lock, is described as an altered or misaligned disk-condyle structural relationship that is maintained during mandibular translation. It is characterized by a lack of joint noise and limited jaw motion. After an acute episode, which can be extremely painful, the chronic condition can become non-painful with the range of motion approximately normal. The finding from a 30 year follow-up study by de Leeuw et al (1994) revealed that over that time very few reducing

displaced disk cases progressed to a non-reducing stage, but almost all the non-reducing displaced disk cases developed structural bone changes [50].

<p>Table.1 Articular Disorders*</p> <p>Congenital or development disorders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aplasia • Hypoplasia • Hyperplasia • Neuplasia <p>Disk derangement disorders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disk displacement with reduction • Disk displacement without reduction <p>Joint dislocation</p> <p>Inflammatory condition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capsulitis / synovitis • Polyarthritides <p>Non inflammatory (Osteoarthrosis)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Osteoarthritis : primary • Osteoarthritis : secondary <p>Ankylosis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fibrous • Bony <p>Fracture (condylar process)</p>

Adopted from American Academy of Orofacial Pain, McNeill C, editor. Temporomandibular disorders: guidelines for classification, assessment, and management. Chicago: Quintessence, 1993; and Okeson JP, editor. Orofacial Pain: guidelines for assessment, diagnosis, and management. Chicago: Quintessence, 1996.

Dislocation of the TMJ occurs when the condyle becomes positioned anterior and superior to the articular eminence, usually during jaw opening and is unable to return to a closed position. It can be caused by trauma or can be a manifestation of joint hypermobility. This condition is referred to as subluxation if the patient is able to self-manipulate the jaw back to a closed position. It is called open lock or dislocation if a health care provider has to reduce the anterior-positioned condyle. Inflammatory conditions can occur in the synovium (synovitis) and /

or capsule (capsulitis) as a result of local trauma, infection, or degeneration, or as a part of a systemic polyarthritic or collagen diseases. TM joint polyarthritides include rheumatoid arthritis, juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (Still's disease), spondyloarthropathies (ankylosing spondylitis, psoriatic arthritis, infectious arthritis, Reiter's syndrome), crystal-induced disease (gout, hyperuricemia) and autoimmune disorders (lupus erythematosus). Osteoarthritis is a degenerative condition of the joint (non-inflammatory) characterized by deterioration and abrasion of articular tissue and concomitant remodeling of the underlying subchondral bone. Osteoarthritis is classified as primary or idiopathic osteoarthritis when the etiology is unknown and secondary osteoarthritis when an etiologic event or factor can be identified (e.g., gout, Cushing's disease, osteonecrosis, infections, and Charcot's neuropathic pain). Ankylosis of the joint could occur and it is either fibrous or bony adhesions restrict condylar movement. Extrinsic traumatic force can injure all related bony components of the masticatory system. Condylar fracture (intra- or extracapsular) with or without displacement can result in contusion and / or laceration of the articular surfaces, ligaments, and disk, usually with intra-articular hemarthrosis. Sequelae could include synovitis, capsulitis, ankylosis, or osteoarthrosis [41, 42].

Masticatory muscle disorders, which are analogous to other regional or localized muscle disorders in the body, include myofascial pain, myositis, myospasms, unclassified local myalgia, myofibrotic contracture, and neoplasia. Table .2

Table .2 Masticatory muscle disorders*
Myofascial pain
Myositis
Myospasms
Local myalgia-unclassified
Myofibrotic contracture
Neoplasm

* Adopted from American Academy of Orofacial Pain, McNeill C, editor, temporomandibular disorders: guidelines for classification, assessment, and management. Chicago: Quintessence, 1993; and Okeson JP, editor. Orofacial Pain: guidelines for assessment, diagnosis, and management.

Myofascial pain is characterized by a localized or regional, dull aching pain, presence of localized tender spots (trigger points) in muscle, tendons, or fascia that reproduce pain on palpation. A characteristic pattern of localized tenderness and regional referred pain on palpation is associated with myofascial pain and differentiates it from the more generalized tenderness in many sites of the body associated with fibromyalgia. A great deal of study and debate continues regarding the similarities and differences of these two conditions [51]. Inactivation of the trigger point area with local anaesthesia, spray and stretch, or ice usually relieves the pain [52]. The muscle pain may be associated with a localized ischemia, histochemical changes at peripheral nociceptive nerve endings, or central nervous system changes including increased activity within the sympathetic nervous system, or psychologic or emotional changes [53]. Patients diagnosed with myofascial pain and other joint conditions had significantly higher levels of depression and somatization than patients diagnosed with only disk displacement [3].

Myositis is an acute, painful, generalized inflammation and swelling of usually the entire muscle. Clinically the patient usually exhibits a marked limited range of motion. Myositis is usually the result of local causes such as infection or trauma. While myospasm (acute trismus, splinting, or cramping) is an acute disorder caused by involuntary, sudden, tonic contraction of a muscle resulting in a marked limitation in the range of motion and pain. The acute pain is present at rest as well as during function. It can be differentiated from other muscle disorders by clinical inspection or fine wire electromyographic verification (EMG). Local myalgia – unclassified which include muscle pain secondary to ischemia, bruxism, fatigue, delayed onset, muscle soreness, autonomic effects, and protective splinting (co-contraction- contraction) that can not be distinguished from the other muscle classifications. Another masticatory muscle disorder is myofibrotic contracture which is a painless shortening of a muscle as result of fibrosis or scarring of the supporting tendons, ligaments, or muscle fibers [41, 42].

Clinical Finding and Diagnosis:

The initial examination for routine dental patients should include procedure and history to determine whether any TMDs exist. Many patients have problems that should be corrected, but they are not aware of the relationship of the TMJ to the health and stability of the dentition and vice versa. A simple screening should be done on every dental patient as part of a complete examination. This include:-

1. Screening Examination:

The screening examination consists of the presence or absence of discomfort in centric relation, and whether upward pressure toward the joint elicits any response of tenderness or tension in centric relation [1]. Evaluating the hinge movement of the mandible, the presence or absence of any difficulty or deviation in mouth opening, joint sounds, pain or tenderness in the muscles of mastication during palpation. Evaluate the harmonization between maximum intercuspation of the teeth and centric relation of the mandible, and examine the teeth for any sign of wear or hypermobility [54].

2. Screening History:

It is helpful to compute the screening examination before the history is taken because the examination often turns up signs of suspected disorders that the examiner can relate to when quizzing patients about their history.

Screening history includes information regarding patient's medical, emotional, socioeconomic status, history of chief complaint which includes onset, duration, and possible exacerbations and remissions of the problem, joint sounds, subluxation or dislocation of the joint, history of arthritis, history of trauma and previous treatment for TMD.

The above examination and screening history should be a routine part of a complete dental examination. If any positive findings are turned up, a more comprehensive examination should be directed at the specific signs and symptoms.

For diagnosing masticatory muscle disorders, seven steps should be followed, and these are: (1) Evaluating muscle tenderness. (2) Ruling out intra-articular problems, this is done by

testing the joints with very firm upward pressure after the condyles are gently positioned into what the operator feels is centric relation and through the use of anterior bite plane. Fig.3

(3) Finding the trigger for occluso-muscle pain, this means the occlusal interferences.

Such interferences can be difficult to discern, but if diagnostic casts are mounted with a carefully made centric bite record, the interference can be found easily. (4) Verifying condyle health and position radiographically. (5) Ruling out gross bone pathosis with radiographs. (6) Ruling out pulpal or periodontal pathosis as sources of pain. (7) Correcting the cause of occluso – muscle pain, occlusal interferences to centric relation (CR) can be eliminated in a reversible or an irreversible manner. Whether a treatment is reversible is only critical when the outcome of treatment is in doubt. Thus reversible methods of treatment realistically fall more into the category of diagnostic procedures. It's really a way of testing a treatment hypothesis to see if it works before we proceed to do something of an invasive nature.

For diagnosing internal derangement, there are several methods, but a combination of methods is usually necessary in meaningful detail. Some of the most methods, in addition to a detailed history, are as follows: (1) Clinical observation of mandibular movement. (2) Manipulative testing. (3) Auscultation. (4) Palpation. (5) Various radiographic techniques. (6) Axiography (7) Mounted diagnostic casts. (8) Diagnostic occlusal therapy [1, 54].

Fig.3. Anterior deprogrammer to separate posterior teeth with smooth function on anterior teeth.

Management of Temporomandibular Disorder:

The majority of TMD patients achieve good relief of symptoms with a conservative model of noninvasive management [56- 61]. However, the treatment of patients with TMD does not necessarily eliminate the disorder(s) but rather results in the management of the disorder(s). Patients with TMD frequently require managed treatment over extended periods of time because of the multifactorial etiology and the long-term nature of many of these disorders [62, 63].

A multidisciplinary model that includes patient education and self-care, cognitive behavioral intervention, pharmacotherapy, physical therapy, and orthopedic appliance therapy (interocclusal splints) is endorsed for the management of nearly all TMD patients. Historically, treatment of patients with TMD has been divided into phase I and phase II therapy. Phase I include the entire multidisciplinary model that have been mentioned before. Phase II therapy involves treatment such as surgical intervention, orthodontic modification, occlusal therapy or prosthodontic rehabilitation, and it is often

nonreversible [2, 64]. The management goals are similar to those of other orthopedic conditions, namely, reduction of pain, reduction of adverse loading, improvement of function, and restoration of normal, daily activities. The emphasis should be on conservation therapy that facilitates the system's natural healing capacity and treatment that involves the patient in the physical and behavioral management of their own problem. Although individual clinicians are successful in diagnosing the more common TMD problems, a team approach is often required for managing complex chronic TMD problems, in particular for evaluating psychological disorders that may be present [41].

Most importantly, regardless of the approach selected, all therapy should be directed at minimizing aberrant input into the central nervous system, whatever the source, for example, stress or pathology [65]. In this way complete dental care for patients can be provided and fulfill patient needs and desires with respect to appearance, comfort, and function [32].

Patient Education and Self-care:

The success of a self-care program is often enough to control an uncomplicated TMD problem [60]. Instruction in a self-care routine should include the following: rest of masticatory system, habit awareness and modification, and a home physiotherapeutic program [41].

Cognitive Behavioral Intervention:

Cognitive behavioral intervention is an important part of the over all biopsychosocial treatment program for TMD patients [66]. Although simple habits will often reduce when the patient is made aware of them, changing persistent habits may require

comprehensive stress management and counseling programs. Behavioral strategies involving a combination of EMG biofeedback, relaxation techniques, and self-directed lifestyle changes are more effective than any single behavioral treatment procedure [6].

Pharmacotherapy:

The indicated classes of pharmacologic agents include analgesics, anti-inflammatory agents, corticosteroids, anxiolytics, muscle relaxants, and low-dose antidepressants [41].

Physical Medicine:

Physical therapy is an effective treatment for TMD because it helps to relieve musculoskeletal pain, restores normal function, and promotes the repair and regeneration of tissues [67]. Referral and close cooperation with licensed professional therapists is recommended. Physical agents include electrotherapy and ultrasound devices, vapocoolants, anesthetic injections, and acupuncture [68]. Physical medicine applications also involve postural training; include correct jaw posture, exercise therapy, and mobilization [69].

Occlusal Splints:

Splint therapy may be defined as the art and science of establishing neuromuscular harmony in the masticatory system and creating a mechanical disadvantage for parafunctional forces with removable appliances. A properly constructed splint supports a harmonious relation among the muscles of mastication, disk assemblies, joints, ligaments, bones, teeth, and tendons [70].

Occlusal splints, also referred to as orthopedic appliances, intraoral appliances, orthotics, night guards, or

bruxism appliances, have a reported 70% to 90% rate of clinical success [71, 72]. Whereas the treatment effect is somewhat predictable, the explanation of the efficacy of the treatment response is less understood [71]. It is considered to be part of the phase I therapy of TMD that seeks to alleviate pain and improve function and often involves reversible therapy [2, 64]. All splints are classified as either permissive or nonpermissive. A permissive splint [73] allows the teeth to move on the splint unimpeded, which in turn allows the condylar head and disk to function anatomically (fig.4).

A nonpermissive splint has a ramp or “indentations” that position the mandible inferiorly and anteriorly and secure it there (fig.5). Examples of permissive splints include bite planes (anterior jigs, Lucia jig, anterior deprogrammer) (Fig.3) and stabilization splints (flat plane, Tanner, superior repositioning, and centric relation [CR]) (Fig.6). An example of a nonpermissive splint is a repositioning splint (anterior repositioning appliance [ARA]) (Fig.7).

Properly fabricated splints have at least six functions including the following:

- (1) To relax the muscles. Occlusal splints are a means of reversibly altering the occlusion to reduce masticatory muscle activity. Fuchs [74] reported the advantages of splint therapy in the reduction of nocturnal EMG masseter activity in patients with TMD. Beard and Clayton [75] also reported reductions in muscle symptoms with splint therapy. Okeson et al [76] found that acute or chronic symptoms of muscle hyperactivity were lessened significantly with 24-hour splint wear. The effectiveness of splint therapy in reducing pain indexes and

muscle hyperactivity is well documented [70, 77-79].

(2) To allow the condyle to seat in CR. This can be achieved if the lateral pterygoid muscle completely relaxes because of its attachment to the disk through the superior belly. Therefore, the condyle-disk assembly will maintain its normal healthy relationship to each other.

(3) To provide diagnostic information. If a patient rapidly becomes comfortable with a splint, it may be an indication that the disorder is muscular. If symptoms worsen with permissive splint wear, this may indicate an internal derangement (disk) problem (perhaps caused by free reign of the condylar head back to the retrodiscal tissues without housing by the disk) [1, 70].

(4) To protect teeth and associated structures from bruxism. Gibbs et al [80] found that the highest recorded bite force during bruxism was 975 lbs. and that bite strength in some bruxer-clenchers can be as much as 6 times that of the nonbruxer. Holmgren et al [81] have shown that splints do not stop bruxism but do redistribute the load borne by the teeth and masticatory system [82, 83].

(5) To mitigate periodontal ligament proprioception.

(6) To reduce cellular hypoxia levels. In a study by Nitzan [84], pressure was measured in the superior joint space of patients with articular disk displacements. When they clenched maximally, recorded pressures reached up to 200 mm Hg. When a flat plane appliance was placed, no significant pressure (no capillary hyperfusion pressure) was recorded. This lends credence to stabilization splint therapy from a molecular point of view.

Determination of the appropriate type of splint therapy depends on the specific diagnosis of the TMD and a thorough understanding of the anatomy of the condyle/disk complex. Muscle incoordination is usually treated with bite plane therapy or permissive splint therapy in phase I (reversible treatment) and with appropriate phase II therapy to restore balance from/to the CR position. Muscle and disk incoordination has the same signs and symptoms as muscle incoordination except reciprocal clicking or a history of reciprocal clicking that stops. Treatment usually includes permissive splint therapy and Phase II therapy for stabilization because of the weak ligament structure [70].

Splints cannot do 3 basic things: unload the joint, prevent bruxism, or “heal” the patient. Some authors and lecturers have stated that splints function to unload the joints and therefore take pressure off the disk. This theory has been disproved by Kuboki et al [85] and cannot be explained anatomically or physiologically. The elevator muscles are located behind the most posterior tooth and therefore ensure that the joint will always be loaded when the elevators contract. Splints do not prevent bruxism; they balance the force distribution to the entire masticatory system. They can decrease the frequency but not the intensity of bruxing episodes [81]. Splints also do not heal patients; they give patients the opportunity to heal themselves. The patient pays not for the fabrication of a splint only but also for the care, skill, and judgment of the practitioner whose goal is to enable healing through appropriate design, monitoring, and adjustment [70].

Fig.4. Permissive splint

Fig.5. Nonpermissive splint.

Fig.6. Occlusal view of mandibular stabilization appliance.

Fig.7. Repositioning appliance locking condyle into anteroinferior position (top). Occlusal view of appliance with indentations in acrylic (bottom).

Occlusal Therapy:

Occlusion is an important factor for restorative dentistry and prosthodontics and therefore requires evaluation to ensure optimal stability of the stomatognathic system. However, if occlusal therapy is deemed necessary to complete treatment of a patient with TMD, the treatment should only be completed after the patient's pain has been significantly relieved and the range of motion substantially improved. The maxillomandibular relationship,

neuromuscular activity, and psychosocial status of the patient must be as stable as possible before proceeding with treatment [86]. Proper treatment sequencing is essential, including pretreatment with an interocclusal appliance, ancillary dental treatment, appropriately timed appointments, and prolonged provisional treatment and cementation. The cardinal rule should be to proceed carefully, using the least invasive procedure possible [41]. When prosthodontic rehabilitation is required in a patient who is having musculoskeletal facial pain, the first obligation of the clinician is to differentially diagnose the pain. Clinicians should take a cautious approach to the timing of restorative treatment in patients who are experiencing musculoskeletal pain. The validity of the maxillomandibular registration is questionable [87].

The occlusal scheme must be integrated with and conform to the remaining tissues of the masticatory system at the time of treatment. This newly established functional equilibrium may be the most optimum physiologic relationship for that particular masticatory system even though the morphologic relationship may not be ideal [88].

On the other hand, if a functional equilibrium has not been established, or if the intercuspal position (ICP) and / or the vertical dimension of occlusion (VDO) are unacceptable or need to be altered to perform necessary dental treatment, the treatment may need to be re-established. When an occlusal scheme has to be re-established, a treatment reference position must be established, namely CR to allow the clinician to design treatment from a known starting

point and to evaluate the progress and the outcome of the treatment on the basis of that starting point [41].

The specific treatment objectives that are desired from an optimum structural and functional re-establishment stand point for all patients [89] including TMD patients are as follows: (1) Maximum symmetrical distribution of intercuspal contacts in the predetermined jaw relationship. (2) Axial or near axial loading of the teeth. (3) An acceptable occlusal plane. (4) Guidance contacts that allow freedom during closing and excursive gliding mandibular movement without deflection of the mandible or teeth. (5) An acceptable vertical dimension of occlusion and interocclusal resting range.

Surgery:

Temporomandibular surgery is the indicated treatment for a very small percentage of TMD patients and only those with specific TMD articular disorders. Surgical management may vary from closed surgical procedures (arthrocentesis and arthroscopy) or open surgical procedures (arthrotomy) to subcondylar osteotomies (condylotomy). A pre-operative and post-operative nonsurgical management should be integrated with the surgical treatment into an over all multidisciplinary treatment approach [41].

Summary:

The clinicians have the responsibility to understand, diagnose TMD conditions, provide treatment, monitor the condition and refer the patient to another practitioner if necessary. Prosthodontists have an important role in occlusal therapy. They should take a cautious approach to the timing of restorative treatment as well as

careful evaluation for the maxillomandibular relationship

Reference:-

1. Dawson PE. Evaluation, diagnosis, and treatment of occlusal problems. 2nd edi. St. Louis: Elsevier; 1989.
2. McNeill C. Temporomandibular disorders-guidelines for classification, assessment and management. 2nd ed. Chicago: Quintessence Publishing Co, 1993.
3. Adrian UJ, Ee Kiam C, and Hee Hon T. Depression and somatization in patient with temporomandibular disorders. J Prosth Dent 2002, 88(5), 479-84.
4. Okeson JP, ed. Orofacial pain: guidelines for assessment, disease, and management. Chicago: Quintessence Publishing Co, 1996.
5. Rugh JD, Solberg WK. Oral health status in the United States: temporomandibular disorders. J Dent Educ 1985, 49, 398-404.
6. Schiffman E, Fricton JR. Epidemiology of TMJ and craniofacial pain. In Fricton JR, Kroening RJ, Hathaway KM, editors. TMJ and craniofacial pain: diagnosis and management. St Louis: IEA Publishers, 1988, 1-10.
7. Dworkin SF, Huggins KH, LeResche L, Von Korff M, Howard J, Truelove E, Sommers E. Epidemiology of signs and symptoms in temporomandibular disorders: clinical signs in cases and controls. J Am Dent Assoc 1990, 120, 273-281.
8. Agerberg G, Inkapööl I. Craniomandibular disorders in an urban Swedish population. J Craniomandib Disord Facial Oral Pain 1990, 4, 154-64.
9. McNeill C. The optimum temporomandibular joint condyle position in clinical practice. Int J Periodont Rest Dent 1985, 6, 53.
10. Howard JA. Temporomandibular joint disorders, facial pain and dental problems of performing artists. In Sataloff R, Brandfonbrener A, Lederman R, editors. Textbook of performing arts medicine. New York: Raven Press, 1990.
11. Schiffman EL, Fricton JR, Haley DP, Shapiro BL. The prevalence and treatment needs of subjects with temporomandibular disorders. J Am Dent Assoc 1990, 120, 295-303.
12. Magnusson T, Carlsson GE, Egermark I. Changes in subjective symptoms of craniomandibular disorders in children and adolescents during a 10-year period. J Orofacial Pain 1993, 7, 76-82.
13. Gunnar E. Carlsson, Tomas Magnusson. Management of temporomandibular disorders in the general dental practice. Chicago: Quintessence Publishing Co; 1999.
14. McNeill C. Craniomandibular (TMJ) disorders - the state of the art. Part II: accepted diagnostic and treatment and modalities. J Prosthet Dent 1983; 49: 393-397.
15. Melzack R, Wall PD. Pain mechanisms: a new theory. Science 1995, 150: 941-949.
16. Gasma A. The role of psychological factors in chronic

- pain. I. A half-century study. *Pain* 1994, 57, 5-15.
17. Sipila K, Veijola J, Jokelainen J, Jarvelin MR, Oikarinen KS, Raustia AM, et al. Association between symptoms of temporomandibular disorders and depression: an epidemiological study of Northern Finland 1966 Birth Cohort. *Cranio* 2001, 19, 183-7.
 18. Rollman GB, Gillespie JM. The role of psychological factors in temporomandibular disorders. *Curr Rev Pain* 2000, 4, 71-81.
 19. Michelotti A, Martina R, Russo M, Romeo R. Personality characteristics of temporomandibular disorder patients using MMPI. *Cranio* 1998, 16, 119-25.
 20. Rudy TE, Turk DC, Kubinski JA, Zaki HS. Differential treatment responses of TMD patients as a function of psychological characteristics. *Pain* 1995, 61, 103-112.
 21. Rugh JD. Psychological factors in the etiology of masticatory pain and dysfunction. In: *The president's conference on the examination, diagnosis and management of temporomandibular disorders*. Chicago: American Dental Association, 1982. p. 85-94.
 22. List T, Dworkin SF. Comparing TMD diagnosis and clinical findings at Swedish and US TMD centers using research diagnostic criteria for temporomandibular disorders. *J Orofacial Pain* 1996, 10, 240-53.
 23. Turk DC, Rudy TE, Kubinski JA, Greco GM. Dysfunctional patients with temporomandibular disorders: evaluating the efficacy of a tailored treatment protocol. *J Consult Clin Psychol* 1996, 64, 139-46.
 24. Clarke NG, Kardachi BJ. The treatment of myofascial pain-dysfunction using the biofeedback principle. *J Periodontol* 1977, 48, 643-5.
 25. Gessel AH. Electromyographic biofeedback and tricyclic antidepressants in myofascial pain-dysfunction syndrome: psychological predictors of outcome. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1975, 91, 1048-52.
 26. Gramling SE, Neblett J, Grayson R, Townsend D. Temporomandibular disorder: efficacy of an oral habit reversal treatment program. *J Behav Ther Exp Psychiatry* 1996, 27, 245-55.
 27. Laskin DM. Etiology of pain-dysfunction syndrome. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1969, 79, 147-53.
 28. Eversole LR, Stone CE, Matheson D, Kaplan H. Psychometric profiles and facial pain. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol* 1985, 60, 269-74.
 29. McCreary CP, Clark GT, Merrill RL, Flack V, Oakley ME. Psychological distress and diagnostic subgroups of temporomandibular disorder patients. *Pain* 1991, 44, 29-34.
 30. Auerbach SM, Laskin DM, Frantsve LME, Orr T. Depression, pain, exposure to stressful life events, and long-term outcomes in temporomandibular disorder patients. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 2001, 59, 628-34.

31. Marbach JJ, Lund P. Depression, anhedonia and anxiety in temporomandibular joint and other facial pain syndromes. *Pain* 1981, 11, 73-84.
32. Michael J. Orofacial pain and occlusion: Is there a link? An overview of current concepts and the clinical implications. *J Prosth Dent* 2005, 39(2), 189-196.
33. The glossary of prosthodontic terms. *J Prosth Dent* 2005, 94(1).10-92.
34. Costen Jb. Syndrome of ear and sinus symptoms dependent upon functions of the temporomandibular joint. *An Oto Rhinol Laryngol* 1934,3,1-4.
35. Pullinger A, Hollender L, Solberg WK, Peterson A. A tomographic study of mandibular condyle position in an asymptomatic population. *J Prosth Dent* 1985,53,706.
36. Ross h, Donald J Stephanos K, Richard W, and Mark E. Prevalence of missing posterior teeth and intraarticular temporomandibular disorders. *J Prosth Dent* 2002,87(1),45-50.
37. Posselt U. The physiology of occlusion and rehabilitation, 2nd edi. Blackwell:Oxford,1968.
38. Ramfjord SP and Ash MM. Occlusion.3rd edi.Philadelphia:W.B. saunders, 1983.
39. Rugh JD, Harlan J. Nocturnal bruxism and temporomandibular disorders. *Adv Neurol* 1988, 49,329-41.
40. Rugh JD. Psychological components of pain. *Dent Clin North Am* 1987,31,579-94.
41. McNeill C. Management of temporomandibular disorders: Concepts and contrivesies. *J Prosth Dent* 1997,77(5),510-22.
42. James P, Gilles J, Ronald D, and Barry J. Orofacial pain: from basic science to clinical management. The tranfere of knowledge in pain research. Quintessence Publishing Co.2001.
43. Sanchez Aniceto G, Garcia Penin A, de la Mata Pages R, Montalvo Moreno JJ. Tumors metastatic to the mandible: analysis of nine cases and review of the literature. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 1990, 48,246-51.
44. Bavitz JB, Chewning LC. Malignant disease as temporomandibular joint dysfunction: review of the literature and report of case. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1990,120,163-6.
45. Farrar WB. Differentiation of temporomandibular joint dysfunction to simplify treatment. *J Prosthet Dent* 1972, 28,629-36.
46. Dolwick MF. Diagnosis and etiology of internal derangements of the temporomandibular joint. In Laskin D, Greenfield W, Gale E, et al, editors. The President's Conference on the examination, diagnosis and management of temporomandibular joint disorders. Chicago: Am Dent Assoc 1983:112-7.
47. Hansson TL. Temporomandibular joint anatomical findings relevant to the clinician. In Clark GT, Solberg WK, editors. Perspectives in

- temporomandibular disorders. Chicago: Quintessence Publishing Co, 1987:45-57.
48. Carlsson GE, Oberg T. Remodeling of the temporomandibular joints. *Oral Sci Rev* 1974, 4, 53-86.
 49. Moffett BC, Johnson LC, McCabe JB, Askew HC. Articular remodeling in the adult human temporomandibular joint. *Am J Anat* 1964, 115,119-42.
 50. de Leeuw R, Boering G, Stegenga B, de Bont LG. Clinical signs of TMJ osteoarthritis and internal derangement 30 years after nonsurgical treatment. *J Orofacial Pain* 1994, 8, 18-24.
 51. Friction JR. Myofacial pain syndrome: characteristics and epidemiology. In: Friction JR, Awad EA, editors. *Advances in pain research and therapy*, vol 17. Myofacial pain and fibromyalgia. New York: Raven Press, 1990:107-27.
 52. McMillan AS, Blasberg B. Pain-pressure threshold in painful jaw muscles following trigger point injection. *J Orofacial Pain* 1994, 8,384-90.
 53. Mense S. Nociception from skeletal muscle in relation to clinical muscle pain. *Pain* 1993, 54,241-89.
 54. Dolwick MG, and Riggs RR: Diagnosis and treatment of internal derangements of the temporomandibular joint. *Dent Clin North Am* 1983,27,561.
 55. Gilboe D: Centric relation as the treatment position. *J Prosth Dent* 1983,50(5),685-89.
 56. Apfelberg DB, Lovey E, Janetos G, Maser MR, Lash H. Temporomandibular joint disease. Results of a ten-year study. *Post Graduate Med* 1979, 65,167-72.
 57. Greene CS, Laskin DM. Long term status of TMJ clicking in patients with myofascial pain dysfunction. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1988, 117,461-5.
 58. Carlsson GE. Long-term effects of treatment of craniomandibular disorders. *J Craniomandib Pract* 1985, 3,337-42.
 59. Okeson JP, Hayes DK. Long-term results of treatment for temporomandibular disorders: an evaluation by patients. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1986, 112,473-8.
 60. Hodges JM. Managing temporomandibular joint syndrome. *Laryngoscope* 1990, 100, 60-6.
 61. Randolph CS, Greene CS, Moretti R, Forbes D, Perry HT. Conservative management of temporomandibular disorders: a posttreatment comparison between patients from a university clinic and from private practice. *Am J Orthod Dentofac Orthop* 1990, 98, 77-82.
 62. Parker MW: A dynamic model of etiology in temporomandibular disorders. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1990,120,283-90.
 63. Okeson JP: Management of temporomandibular disorders and occlusion,3rd ed. St Louis, MO, Mosby, 1993.
 64. Baragona PM, Cohen HV: Long-term orthopedic appliance therapy. *Dent Clin North Am* 1991, 35,109-21.
 65. Sessle BJ. Acute and chronic craniofacial pain: brainstem

- mechanisms of nociceptive transmission and neuroplasticity and their clinical correlates. *Crit Rev Oral Biol Med* 2000, 11, 57-91
66. Clark GT, Seligman DA, Solberg WK, Pullinger AG. Guidelines for the treatment of temporomandibular disorders. *J Craniomandib Disord Facial Oral Pain* 1990, 4, 80-8.
 67. Danzig W, Van Dyke AR. Physical therapy as an adjunct to temporomandibular joint therapy. *J Prosthet Dent* 1983, 49, 96-9.
 68. Lark MR, Gangarosa LP Sr. Iontophoresis: an effective modality for the treatment of inflammatory disorders of the temporomandibular joint and myofascial pain. *Cranio* 1990, 8, 108-19.
 69. Au AR, Klineberg IJ. Isokinetic exercise management of temporomandibular joint clicking. *J Prosthet Dent* 1993, 70, 33-9.
 70. Tim J. A common-sense approach to splint therapy. *J Prosth Dent* 2001, 86(5), 539-45.
 71. Clark GT. A critical evaluation of orthopedic interocclusal appliance therapy: design, theory, and overall effectiveness. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1984, 108, 359.
 72. Sheikholeslam A, Holmgren K, Riise C. A clinical and electromyographic study of the long-term effects of an occlusal splint on the temporal and masseter muscles in patients with functional disorders and nocturnal bruxism. *J Oral Rehabil* 1986, 13, 137-45.
 73. Boero RP. The physiology of splint therapy: a literature review. *Angle Orthod* 1989, 59, 165-80.
 74. Fuchs P. The muscular activity of the chewing apparatus during night sleep. An examination of healthy subjects and patients with functional disturbances. *J Oral Rehabil* 1975, 2, 35-48.
 75. Beard CC, Clayton JA. Effects of occlusal splint therapy on TMJ dysfunction. *J Prosthet Dent* 1980, 44, 324-35.
 76. Okeson JP, Kemper JT, Moody PM. A study of the use of occlusion splints in the treatment of acute and chronic patients with craniomandibular disorders. *J Prosthet Dent* 1982, 48, 708-12.
 77. Manns A, Miralles R, and Guerrero F. The changes in electrical activity of the postural muscles of the mandible upon varying the vertical dimension. *J Prosthet Dent* 1981, 45, 438-45.
 78. Manns A, Miralles R, Santander H, Valdivia J. Influence of the vertical dimension in the treatment of myofascial pain-dysfunction syndrome. *J Prosthet Dent* 1983, 50, 700-9.
 79. Clark GT, Lanham F, Flack VF. Treatment outcome results for consecutive TMJ clinic patients. *J Craniomandib Disord* 1988, 2, 87-95.
 80. Gibbs CH, Mahan PE, Mauderli A, Lundeen HC, Walsh EK.

- Limits of human bite strength. *J Prosthet Dent* 1986,56,226-9.
81. Holmgren K, Sheikholeslam A, Riise C. Effect of a full-arch maxillary occlusal splint on parafunctional activity during sleep in patients with nocturnal bruxism and signs and symptoms of craniomandibular disorders. *J Prosthet Dent* 1993,69,293-7.
 82. Gentz R. Apparatus for recording of bruxism during sleep. *Sven Tandlak Tidskr* 1972, 65,327-42.
 83. Kydd WL, Daly C. Duration of nocturnal tooth contacts during bruxing. *J Prosthet Dent* 1985, 53,717-21.
 84. Nitzan DW. Intraarticular pressure in the functioning human temporomandibular joint and its alteration by uniform elevation of the occlusal plane. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 1994,52,671-9.
 85. Kuboki T, Takenami Y, Orsini MG, Maekawa K, Yamashita A, Azuna Y, et al. Effect of occlusal appliances and clenching on the internally deranged TMJ space. *J Orofac Pain* 1999, 13,38-48.
 86. McNeill C, ed. Current controversies in temporomandibular disorders. Chicago: Quintessence Publishing Co, 1992.
 87. Ales Oberz and Jens C. Turp. The effect of musculoskeletal facial pain on registration of maxillomandibular relationships and treatment planning: A synthesis of the literature. *J Prosth Dent* 1998;79:439-45.
 88. Stohler CS. Clinical decision-making in occlusion: a paradigm shift. In McNeill C, editor. *The science and practice of occlusion*. Carol Stream: Quintessence Publishing Co; 1997 (In press).
 89. McNeill C. Fundamental treatment goals. In McNeill CM, editor. *The science and practice of occlusion*. Carol Stream: Quintessence Publishing Co; 1997 (In press).